

THE SYSTEM OF HIGHER AND SECONDARY SPECIALIZED TRAINING AND ADVANCED TRAINING FOR INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: This article provides information on the activities of higher and secondary specialized training institutions for personnel training in the internal affairs bodies, as well as the activities of the Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in improving the professional skills of serving employees, in order to ensure the development of society and peace and tranquility of the people after the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence.

Key words: Ministry of internal affairs, akdamiya of Internal Affairs, akadimik lyceums of Internal Affairs, Tashkent higher military technical knowledge institution, Tashkent fire safety Higher School, Institute of professional development of work

On the basis of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 447 dated September 2, 1994 and the Order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 264 dated October 20, 1994, the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established on the basis of the Higher and Secondary Special Police Schools of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered one of the largest higher educational institutions in Central Asia for training personnel for law enforcement agencies and is included in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The Academy carries out its activities in accordance with the Charter. Lecture courses were published, a regulatory and legal framework for the organization of the educational process was created.

In 1995-1997, a new stage began in the development of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the educational process was further improved. Editorial and publishing activities were revived, and certain work was carried out to provide students with textbooks and study guides written in the state language. Since 1998, the educational work carried out at the Academy has been fundamentally reformed on the basis of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted in 1997 and the National Program for Personnel Training. Scientific research work has been expanded and focused on organizing and conducting fundamental and applied research in the field of strengthening legality, law and order in internal affairs bodies, combating crime, and protecting human rights. Doctoral and master's degree programs have been intensified, and a new generation of Uzbek legal scholars has been formed. A Higher Academic Course has been established within the educational institution on the basis of the Faculty for Training Management Personnel for Internal Affairs Bodies. Here, management personnel of the internal affairs bodies system are being trained. A new approach has been adopted in the work of the faculty for advanced training of officers of internal affairs bodies, based on the

requirements and tasks of the time and taking into account the experience of police departments of foreign countries. The visit of our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs on June 29, 2017 was a truly historic event. During the visit, it was determined as a priority task to increase the prestige and status of the educational institution by implementing the plans set out in the action strategy for 2017-2021, strengthen its material and technical base, improve the system of training highly qualified personnel, and transform the academy into a completely new educational institution.

In particular, the President's resolution of August 16, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of employees of internal affairs bodies" further strengthened the legal framework of the sector. Based on the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of December 1, 2017 No. 958 "On approval of the regulations on the procedure for selecting and admitting candidates to full-time and part-time forms of education of the bachelor's degree of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan", full-time and part-time bachelor's degree programs were established at the Academy of Internal Affairs to train professional personnel.

Another innovation is that starting from the 2020-2021 academic year, admission to the full-time form of education of the academy will be carried out only from among graduates of academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, military-academic lyceums, as well as employees of internal affairs bodies.

The Higher Technical School of Fire Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which trains personnel for fire safety departments, which are an important part of the internal affairs system, was established on the basis of the Tashkent Faculty and Tashkent Fire-Technical Schools of the former USSR, in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic No. 404 dated August 11, 1993, on the basis of the Tashkent Faculty of the Higher Technical Engineering School of Fire Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The Higher Technical School of Fire Safety is a specialized higher educational institution engaged in the training and advanced training of highly qualified specialists with high professional skills for internal affairs departments, capable of effectively performing the tasks of ensuring fire safety, extinguishing and preventing fires, ensuring the safety of the population, protecting and preserving material assets.

With the adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" on August 29, 1997, the development of state educational standards was set as the main task for all educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 1997, the first graduates graduated from the center. In the form of full-time education, 223 engineers with higher education in the specialty "Fire Safety", 665 technicians with secondary specialized education in the specialty "Fire Safety Technician", 23 technicians with secondary specialized education in the specialty "Electrical Communications Technician" in the profession "Operation of Automated Communication and Signaling Systems" graduated. Also, 284 fire safety engineers in the specialty "Fire Safety", 70 higher education specialists in the "Fire Safety Technique" engineer and 197 qualified personnel with secondary specialized education in the specialty "Fire Safety" in the specialty "Organization of Fire Protection and Its Techniques" were trained in the form of correspondence education.

During 1998-2001, a total of 1,159 highly qualified specialists in such areas and specialties as "Fire Safety" and "Organization of Fire Prevention Work", "Organization of

Emergency Services", "Operation of Automated Communication and Signaling Systems", "Electrical Communication Technician" and "Organization of Fire Protection and Its Techniques", and a total of 262 bachelors with higher education were trained in correspondence education.

Over the past period, extensive work has been carried out to improve the system of internal affairs bodies. In particular, a certain system has been formed in our country for the training of specialists of the State Fire Safety Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, scientific and pedagogical personnel in the postgraduate education system, and for the implementation of scientific research activities in the field of fire safety. The measures taken have made it possible to staff fire safety units with personnel who have undergone special professional training and are capable of independently implementing measures in the field of State Fire Supervision, fire prevention and fire extinguishing. The charter of the higher school was developed on the basis of the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2013 No. VMQ-272 "On Approval of the Regulation on State Fire Supervision". In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF 5005 dated April 10, 2017, the higher school was transformed into the Institute of Fire Safety. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 23, 2017 No. PQ-2991 "On the radical improvement of the activities of fire safety units of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan", including the charter of the institute, was approved. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2019 No. PF -5706, the Main Department of Fire Safety and the Fire Safety Institute within the ministry were transferred to the Ministry of Emergency Situations and transformed into the Academy of the Ministry of Emergency Situations.

Tashkent Higher Military Technical Educational Institution was taken under the jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov dated January 10, 1992 and included in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. The educational institution accepted the first batch of cadets in 1991 and trained the first graduates in 1995. The activities of the educational institution are carried out on the basis of the Charter. It is considered a training military unit in the deployment plans of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a reserve of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, intended to strengthen public order and security, and perform other operational service tasks within the framework of the plan to protect the Tashkent defense area in the event of an escalation of the operational situation.

The structure of the educational institution The organizational and staff structure of the Tashkent Higher Military Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 23, 2004 No. 356-57 "On measures to increase the effectiveness of personnel training at the Tashkent Higher Military Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan". The educational institution organizationally consists of a department, main educational units, departments, and supply units. It includes a headquarters, cadet battalions, a faculty of advanced training, a battalion for ensuring the educational process, 16 departments, more than 10 departments and services.

The Tashkent Higher Military Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan trains personnel for the troops of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the

Republic of Uzbekistan and relevant internal affairs departments, as well as other military departments and law enforcement agencies on the basis of plans and orders. Graduates of the educational institution are awarded the military rank of lieutenant, a diploma of a specialist with higher education and a driver's license of categories B, C. The period of study at the educational institution is included in the service (labor) experience. During the study period, cadets are provided with free accommodation, meals, clothing, scholarships and other benefits in accordance with the established norms. On December 14, 2015, in accordance with the Resolution of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 2740 "On approval of the Regulations on training and retraining courses for employees of organizations authorized to carry and use departmental firearms and special means on the basis of the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical Educational Institution of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan", a system of advanced training in the use of firearms for all employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs was established. In April 2017, the Tashkent Higher Military-Technical School of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was reorganized into the Military-Technical Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2017 No. PF-5005 "On measures to radically increase the efficiency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, strengthen their responsibility in ensuring public order, reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens". After the establishment of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan in August 2017, based on the need to train qualified and professional personnel for the sector, in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 2017, the Military-Technical Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan was transferred to the jurisdiction of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In order to improve the skills of personnel serving in the internal affairs bodies, to teach and implement foreign experience in combating crime and maintaining public order, the Resolution No. PF-3216 of August 16, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of employees of internal affairs bodies" and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev of August 23, 2018 No. PQ-3919 "On measures to introduce an effective system of management, control and work with personnel of internal affairs bodies" established the Institute for Advanced Training and its 14 branches in the field. In particular, over the past period, the qualifications of about 9 thousand employees and more than 5,700 assistants of preventive inspectors were improved within the framework of 60 mobile training camps held by the Institute's professors and teachers in the field branches. At the end of the training camps, a system of issuing certificates to employees who successfully mastered the training programs was established.

The Nukus "Temurbeklar Maktabi" Military Academic Lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan began its activities in accordance with the Resolution of the Head of our state dated June 28, 2019 "On additional measures to educate adolescents in the spirit of military patriotism and improve the system of training personnel for the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Civil Service". The main focus of the Military Academic Lyceum is on educating students to be mentally and physically mature, possessing high patriotic, spiritual and moral qualities, initial professional knowledge and skills necessary for employees of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and law

enforcement agencies, as well as on targeted in-depth preparation for admission to higher military educational institutions. In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of employees of the internal affairs bodies", by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated September 26, 2017 No. 767 "On measures to organize the activities of Academic Lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan", 14 academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs were established, one in each region of the republic. The tasks of academic lyceums were determined to be targeted in-depth preparation for admission to higher educational institutions of the internal affairs bodies.

The best students are selected for academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs through entrance exams and competitions. Educational programs may include the following areas:

- **Law:** Students gain in-depth knowledge in areas such as legal theories, criminal, civil and administrative law.

- **Psychology and Communication:** Psychological preparation for employees of the Ministry of Internal Affairs to make the right decisions when faced with social interaction and stressful situations.

- **Physical training:** Physical activity and training are important factors that help maintain the health and strength of police officers.

In academic lyceums, teachers are highly qualified specialists, experienced lawyers and psychologists, who teach students not only knowledge, but also practical skills. Teachers and trainers provide students with not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical approaches to solving modern legal and social problems.

The main areas of activity of the academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs:

1. Personnel training:

Lyceums provide students with in-depth knowledge in areas such as law, criminology, security services, and maintaining discipline.

Students are taught legal culture, respect for the law, and practical skills in maintaining legal order in society.

2. Academic education:

Lyceum students, along with general education subjects (mathematics, physics, chemistry, history, etc.), also receive knowledge in special subjects related to the Ministry of Internal Affairs.

Students are given tests, practical exercises, and training to improve their professional skills.

3. Practical training:

Students are provided with opportunities to carry out practical activities related to the internal affairs system, including studying law enforcement activities and participating in processes.

Students are given opportunities to get to know the organizations in the Ministry of Internal Affairs system closely, as well as practical exercises related to working in the law enforcement system.

4. Physical and moral preparation:

Students increase their physical potential by strengthening physical fitness, participating in sports and competitions.

In lyceums, great attention is paid to preparing students not only intellectually, but also morally, since high moral and spiritual qualities are necessary for employees of the Internal Affairs System.

Students of academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs are directed to practice in order to consolidate their theoretical knowledge. During this process, students study the activities of the internal affairs system in more depth and test their knowledge in real conditions. Students can, for example, do internships in police departments, law firms, or other law enforcement organizations. Graduates of the academic lyceum of the Ministry of Internal Affairs are given preferential admission to higher educational institutions of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Emergency Situations on the basis of additional points in the amount of 10 percent of the highest score they can score during their tests, and are accepted into service in the internal affairs bodies, the security service of the National Guard, and the fire and rescue units of the Ministry of Emergency Situations, respectively, in the order determined by the heads of law enforcement agencies. In conclusion, during the years of independence, a system of training qualified specialists for internal affairs bodies was created. The Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is a leading educational institution in this regard. Tashkent Higher Technical School and Tashkent Higher School of Fire Safety have trained personnel in addition to the academy. Since 2017, academic lyceums of the Ministry of Internal Affairs have been established and launched their activities in order to train secondary specialized personnel for the sector. The Qualification Institute has been established to improve the qualifications of employees serving in the sector and is operating on the basis of the goals set for itself. Today, the training of patriotic, loyal and comprehensively qualified personnel is relevant, and large-scale work is being carried out in our country in this regard.

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